

Open Science NL Open Research Software Advisory Panel

Meeting Notes

29 November 2024, 15:00 - 17.00 CET (UTC + 1:00)

Location: MS Teams

Attendees

- Ana Martinovici
- Daniel S. Katz
- Daniela Gawehns
- John Swinbank
- Laurents Sesink
- Mateusz Kuzak
- Martine de Vos
- Morane Gruenpeter
- Santosh Ilamparuthi
- Thomas Pronk
- Vincent Traag
- Mark van Assem - Acting Co-Chair
- Marta Teperek - Acting Chair

Apologies:

- Karthik Ram
- Maria Cruz, Chair

15.00 - 15.05 – Welcome and agenda

Members of the panel and Mark van Assem, who is the acting Co-Chair, introduce themselves. The agenda is accepted.

15.05 – 15.10 – Approval of minutes and terms

There are no objections; the minutes and terms are approved and will be published / updated on Zenodo and linked from the OSNL website.

15.10 – 15.20 - Work Programme 2024 and 2025: implementation update

MT gave a short update (presentation) on the implementation of the Work Programme 2024 and 2025:

- Due to budget cuts, financial instruments which were not approved or announced yet are still uncertain. The OSNL Steering Board still needs to decide on how to allocate funding to these instruments.
- Points of attention (specific for software):
 - Decisions on awards for the “Strengthening local and thematic DCCs” call will be made 13 December. After the decisions have been made, Open Science NL would like to meet with the community to get feedback on the call and on the process.

- Budget that was not spent in the call for proposals “Strengthening local and thematic DCCs” is used to support the creation of DCCs at universities/regions, which have not yet received funding for this purpose from NWO or OSNL.
- The “Software sustainability call” is under discussion. It is a high priority, and there will be funding available, but how much is still uncertain. Also the practical implementation (how and when) is being discussed with the NLeSC.
- Proposals received in the Recognition and Rewards of Open Science call for proposals will be decided on the 13th of December. The call gives institutions 50k€ to define their own plan on how to implement Open Science in their hiring and promotion policies.
- The fact that the outcomes and impacts of the activities launched/to be launched in the Work Programme 2024 -2025 are not yet known (and will not be known for a few years to come), presents a challenge with regards to the planning of activities for the new Work Programme.

15.30 - 16.55 – Development of a Work Programme 2026 and 2027 and reflections on the community consultation:

MT gave a short overview (presentation) about the [outcomes of the community consultation](#) on the new Work Programme ideas, explained the overall framework for the design of the work programme and opened the floor to comments and discussion from the panel.

Main suggestions and reflections shared by the members of the panel were:

Sustainability of projects’ outcomes/free and open source software and infrastructures

Sustainability of projects’ outcomes/free and open source software and infrastructures are indeed a challenge and it is difficult to get funding for maintenance. Perhaps financial contributions to such initiatives could be made available as part of regular grant applications (as some form of cost, or even a donation?), through dedicated calls for projects or scaling up grants, or by somehow allocating tokens for usage, so that awarded projects that use free and open source have a way to indicate which software they use and help support it? Furthermore, sometimes reusing is challenging if it has not been designed with re-use in mind. The fact that there is limited funding available for maintaining, contributing to or reusing existing software, combined with incentives which often favour new developments, rather than using something which already exists, further complicates the situation. Reuse might be increased if calls explicitly encourage it (instead of focusing on new code), by creating a “parasite award” and by training researchers to create reusable code.

Job profiles and recognition of RSE work

It has been acknowledged that there are a lot of challenges in the implementation of job profiles for research software engineers and with regards to the recognition of their contributions. This could be partially addressed by explaining the nature of the work of such professionals and also how they contribute to impact. Better recognition of these roles (including raising awareness and enabling connections between the role holders and people who have and who don’t have certain skills) could eventually also help address the capacity gap. Such roles should also be available to people coming from diverse backgrounds (having a PhD might not need to be a requirement). Furthermore, close collaboration between researchers and research support professionals is needed to build understanding and appreciation of each other’s contributions, but also to provide more clarity on responsibilities. Mobility between roles should also be encouraged, not only within academia (research and research support roles), but also between academia and industry.

Skills development

Traineeships with FOSS organisations could not only help the sustainability of FOSS, but also facilitate skills building by trainees and making new connections (networking).

Overview of existing infrastructures

Panel members believed that while creating an overview of existing infrastructures could provide information on where the gaps are, it is not a suitable solution for solving the challenge of fragmented infrastructures. Such overviews are never complete and are quickly out of date.

Recognising and rewarding open science practices

This is seen as one of the key challenges to be addressed. For open science practices to be recognised and rewarded, including as part of grant applications. While this is an issue in general, an observation was made that NWO devotes a lot of attention to open access to publications and to data management plans, but doesn't evaluate open science practices as part of the grant application, and also doesn't follow up with grantees to validate if outputs have been indeed made openly available. This should be changed as soon as possible for open sciences practices to become the norm.

Recommendations for prioritisation of ideas

Scope of the challenges should be taken into account. Global problems cannot be solved through purely local efforts. However, for some global challenges (e.g. recognition and rewards of open science), important improvements can be made locally, which could act as an example to other countries and organisations.

Potential gaps

Panel members listed several topics which were not (sufficiently) addressed during the consultation. These included:

- FAIR, especially the interoperability and reusability issues;
- Reproducibility of research and research workflows, and the tools that are needed to improve reproducibility;
- Standardisation of software management plans;
- Open hardware;
- More attention should be devoted also to smaller pieces of code that researchers use to do analyses when writing scientific papers, and also to promoting their scale up and reuse (micro-projects).

Concern about the representativeness of the community consultation

Panel members have raised a concern with regards to the representativeness of the community consultation workshop attendees, in particular with regards to audiences from the humanities and applied research. The attendees consisted primarily of research support staff and infrastructure providers, with only around 25% being researchers. MT explained that ideally another consultation could take place, but the capacity within the OSNL office is limited, so it might not be possible.

16.55 - 17.00 - Meeting close and plans for upcoming next meetings

- Meeting in Q1/Q2 2025:
 - First ideas on how to turn community input into financial instruments
 - Work Programme 2024 and 2025 implementation update
- Meeting in Q3 2025:
 - Feedback on the draft Work Programme 2026 and 2027

Meeting close

- MT closed the meeting at 17.00 hrs CET.

Resources shared:

- Outcome of community consultation about research software at UMCs:
<https://blog.esciencecenter.nl/how-is-research-software-managed-at-umcs-insights-from-a-first-meetup-4181e9626a60>
- Symposium of the Dutch Reproducibility Network on 6 December:
<https://reproducibilitynetwork.nl/event/nlrnsymposium2024/>
- Collection of academic job offers which mentioned open science: <https://osf.io/7jbnt/>
- Make-or-buy decisions in research and research software - blog post by Daniel S. Katz:
<https://danielskatzblog.wordpress.com/2023/12/07/make-or-buy-decisions/>
- Data and Software Management Plans must be public and should be machine-readable - blog post by Daniel S. Katz:
<https://danielskatzblog.wordpress.com/2016/04/13/data-and-software-management-plans-must-be-public-and-should-be-machine-readable/>